

Metal Derivatives of Dialkyl Phosphites—Part I

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Reactions of dialkyl phosphites with anhydrous aluminium chloride and aluminium ethoxide have been studied and the products $\text{Al}[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OR})_2]_3$, (I), $\text{Al}[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OR})_2]_2\text{Cl}$ (II) and $(\text{H}_3\text{C}_2\text{O})_3\text{Al}[\text{H} \text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OR})_2]_3$ (III) have been obtained. Infrared spectral study of the compounds have also been made.

Dialkyl phosphites in many of their reactions exist as $(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ ¹. However, there are some reactions which cannot be explained unless the existence of a tautomeric equilibrium is assumed,

(Phosphite form) (Phosphonate form)

similar to the one observed in beta-diketones². Lithium, sodium, potassium and silver derivatives³ of dialkyl phosphites show a complete absence of phosphoryl group, whereas, mercury⁴, platinum⁵, and silicon⁶ derivatives of dialkyl phosphites have metal-phosphorus linkage in them.

In view of the above observations, it was thought of interest to synthesise compounds of different metals with dialkyl phosphites and to study the nature of linkage formed in them. The present paper deals with aluminium derivatives.

Reaction between anhydrous aluminium chloride and dialkyl phosphite both in 1 : 3 molar ratio and in excess of the ligand, in dry benzene, gave white solid (I) (R = Et). In 1 : 2 molar ratio, two atoms of chlorine of aluminium chloride were replaced and a light yellow coloured solid, (II) (R = Et) was obtained. Reactions with other dialkyl phosphites such as dimethyl, dipropyl (normal and iso-), dibutyl (normal) phosphites were also studied. It was necessary to eliminate the hydrogen chloride liberated in the reactions to avoid the following side reaction⁷,

and, therefore, the reactions were carried out under reduced pressure, which may be represented as follows :

The tautomeric forms of the dialkylphosphites suggest that (I) may have the structures (A) or (B).

Similarly compound (II) may have the structures (C) or (D).

The absorptions at 590–362 cm^{-1} in the far infra red region of compounds I ($R = \text{CH}_3$) and II ($R = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) indicate the presence of Al–O–P bond⁸. This rules out the structure B and D.

Though structures A and C would provide the simplest mechanism for the reaction, they are also ruled out in the light of the absorption at 1200–1215 cm^{-1} (Table 1) which has been assigned to P = O group. The normal frequency for P = O group⁹ is at 1280 cm^{-1} . There is a characteristic shift of phosphoryl absorption to lower frequency due to co-ordination of the phosphoryl oxygen to the aluminium of the other molecules as has been observed by earlier workers¹⁰. The presence of P = O group suggests that the structures B and D rapidly rearranged to the structures E and F respectively.

For the formation of E and F following plausible mechanism has been suggested.

Similar type of rearrangement has also been suggested by earlier workers¹⁰.

The absorption at 715 cm^{-1} has been assigned to P–C bond, though this assignment is of doubtful nature¹¹.

Reactions

(1) *Reaction between anhydrous aluminium chloride and dialkyl phosphites in the molar ratio of 1 : 3 and in excess of the ligand in benzene* : Dialkyl phosphite was added slowly to the flask containing anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry benzene with constant shaking and fitted with a water condenser which in turn was connected to a suction pump through a calcium chloride tube. Heat was evolved along with white fumes of HCl gas which became dense on heating. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 60–70° in an oil bath till the reaction subsided (2 hr.). The supernatant liquid was taken in another flask and the residue was washed two or three times with small portions of dry benzene to purify the final product which was then dried under reduced pressure (4 mm) at 70–80°. A white solid was obtained (Table 2; 1–6). The supernatant liquid, on removing the solvent under reduced pressure, gave very small amount of solid, which was less than 0.1 g in each case.

(2) *Reaction between anhydrous aluminium chloride and dialkyl phosphites in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 in dry benzene* : Dialkyl phosphite was added slowly to a flask containing anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry benzene. Similar reduced pressure apparatus was fitted. Heat was evolved along with white fumes of HCl gas which becomes dense on heating. The solution was refluxed in an oil bath controlling the temperature in between 70–80° and refluxing was continued for about 3 hrs. hours till the reaction subsided. The supernatant liquid was decanted off in another flask and the residue, after washing with dry benzene, dried under reduced pressure (4 mm) at 90°. Light yellow solid was obtained (Table 2; 7–9). On removing the solvent from the supernatant liquid by distillation and then drying under reduced pressure, very small amount (0.5–0.9 g) of light yellow solid was obtained.

TABLE 2

S.N.	Reactants	Amount (g)	Product, state & yield(%)	%P		Analysis %Al		%Cl	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	AlCl ₃ (CH ₃ O) ₂ P(O)H	1.59 3.93	Al[P(O)(OCH ₃) ₂] ₃ White solid (91.6)	26.50	26.25	8.02	7.63	—	—
2.	AlCl ₃ (C ₂ H ₅ O) ₂ P(O)H	1.00 6.20	Al[P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ White solid (77.7)	20.67	21.21	5.88	6.16	—	—
3.	AlCl ₃ (C ₂ H ₅ O) ₂ P(O)H	3.00 40.00	Al[P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ White solid (91.4)	22.06	21.21	6.40	6.16	—	—
4.	AlCl ₃ <i>n</i> -(C ₃ H ₇ O) ₂ P(O)H	1.00 3.75	Al[P(O) <i>n</i> -(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂] ₃ White solid (92.0)	18.06	17.80	5.40	5.17	—	—
5.	AlCl ₃ iso-(C ₃ H ₇ O) ₂ P(O)H	2.08 7.75	Al[P(O) iso-(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂] ₃ White solid (83.3)	18.35	17.80	5.64	5.17	—	—
6.	AlCl ₃ <i>n</i> -(C ₄ H ₉ O) ₂ P(O)H	1.00 4.36	Al[P(O) <i>n</i> -(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ White solid (88.3)	15.23	15.33	4.76	4.45	—	—
7.	AlCl ₃ (CH ₃ O) ₂ P(O)H	2.29 3.78	Al[P(O)(OCH ₃) ₂] ₂ Cl Light yellow solid (89.4)	21.60	22.09	9.81	9.62	12.86	12.66
8.	AlCl ₃ (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ P(O)H	3.00 6.20	Al[P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₂ Cl Light yellow solid (92.6)	17.85	18.42	8.50	8.02	11.00	10.55
9.	AlCl ₃ <i>n</i> -(C ₃ H ₇ O) ₂ P(O)H	2.00 5.00	Al[P(O) <i>n</i> -(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂] ₂ Cl Light yellow solid (93.5)	16.29	15.79	7.00	6.88	9.24	9.04

(3) *Reaction between aluminium ethoxide and excess diethyl phosphite in benzene* : Diethyl phosphite was added in small portions with constant shaking to aluminium ethoxide placed in dry benzene in a flask. Very slight heat was produced. The reaction mixture was refluxed on the fractionating column for about 2 hrs. About 50 ml of the benzene was distilled over at the fractionating column. For only few seconds the azeotrope was obtained at 68° and then the temperature rose to 80° showing the presence of only benzene. On cooling a colourless highly viscous solution was obtained. The benzene was removed by distillation and the last traces were removed under reduced pressure. A colourless jelly like viscous liquid was obtained. A very small portion of the viscous liquid on being exposed to air becomes more thick and the compound hydrolyses. Found, Al, 4.34%, P, 16.0%. Required for the Compound $(C_2H_5O)_3Al [HP(O)(C_2H_5O)_2]_3$: Al, 4.68%, P, 16.14%.

The viscous liquid on being kept for long time (3 months) changes from colourless to light green solid. It was again analysed showing no change in the composition.

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